

THE USE OF ANESTHESIA FOR THE PREPARATION OF SINGLE-ROOTED TEETH FOR METAL-CERAMIC CROWNS

Bagirov A.,

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant

Abdulazimova G.,

Department of Orthopedic Dentistry Assistant

Ismayilova H.

Azerbaijan Medical University,

Department of Orthopedic Dentistry Assistant

Baku, Azerbaijan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8348695>

Abstract

When preparing for metal-ceramic crowns of single root teeth, paraapical infiltration anesthesia was performed. This technique ensures the effectiveness and safety of the injection [1,8,9]. Plus, a significantly smaller amount of anesthetic. Anesthesia is performed using a standard cartridge syringe.

Keywords: anesthesia of individual single-rooted teeth, standard cartridge syringe, paraapical anesthesia.

For high-quality prosthetics of the oral cavity, non-painful orthopedic interventions are of great importance. Today, the problem of choosing anesthesia in orthopedic dentistry is especially relevant, since the number of manufacturing metal-ceramic crowns, the main component of most removable and non-removable structures, is increasing. It is very important for a dentist to decide on the method of anesthesia, which depends on the amount of hard tooth the preparation of teeth with preserved pulp in the process of manufacturing metal-ceramic crowns usually requires anesthesia [1,2].

Injection anesthesia is the leading method of pain relief during orthopedic interventions. Effective anesthesia is important not only for the cessation of pain, but as a preventive measure for the prevention of injuries to tissues and organs of the oral cavity, which can occur during various movements of the patient in response to pain during tooth preparation. It is also important to choose the right anesthetic and appropriate injection anesthesia, given the complexity of the injection and its safety for the patient [1,3]. In the process of preparing teeth for metal-ceramic crowns, it becomes necessary to anesthetize both a group of teeth with fixed prosthetics and single teeth, which are more common in the manufacture of removable dentures [4]. For anesthesia of single teeth, which are often located in different quadrants of the upper and lower jaws, it is advisable to use infiltration anesthesia.

In the available literature, there are no clear indications for choosing the method of infiltration anesthesia of individual teeth for preparation: some authors recommend intraligamentary anesthesia, others recommend paraapical injection of an anesthetic under the periosteum, etc. [1,5].

The main requirements for anesthesia of teeth during the preparation process are as follows:

- anesthesia should be long enough for the preparation of hard tissues of the tooth;
- there is no need for deep anesthesia of the pulp, since the intervention is performed only on the hard tissues of the tooth.

The purpose of the work: the choice of an effective and safe injection method (paraapical) anesthesia of individual single-rooted teeth using a standard carpool syringe for their preparation for metal-ceramic crowns.

Material and methods of research.

For the study were selected 44 patients aged 25 to 60 years who were practically healthy and had no contraindications to local anesthesia, and also did not use drugs that affect the pain response. For the purpose of a clinical study of paraapical anesthesia, we performed the indicated anesthesia of 116 individual single-rooted teeth for their preparation for metal-ceramic crowns. For paraapical anesthesia of individual single-rooted teeth with preserved pulp, we used: a standard carpool injector, carpool needles with a diameter of 0.3 mm, a length of 10 mm, and a strong standard anesthetic based on 4% articaine with adrenaline 1: 100,000 ("Ultracain DS Forte") [1,6,7]. "Ultracain DS Forte" is contained in glass carpoles of increased resistance of the company "Hoechst". The high quality of the glass ensures the stability of the cartridge during the high pressure injection that occurs when the anesthetic is injected.

Method of paraapical anesthesia.

An anesthetic solution is injected with a standard carpool injector into the projection area of the root apex of the corresponding single-root tooth from the vestibular and oral sides: - from the vestibular side, 0.2 ml of anesthetic is slowly injected under the mucous membrane, then the needle is advanced further, under the periosteum, into the projection area of the apex of the tooth root and injected under the periosteum, another 0.3 ml of anesthetic (total - 0.5 ml of the drug, which is injected for 30 s);

- on the oral side, anesthesia is carried out in the same way: 0.1 ml of the anesthetic solution is slowly injected under the mucous membrane, then the needle is advanced under the periosteum and 0.2 ml of anesthetic is injected at the apex of the tooth root (total - 0.3 ml of the drug, which is injected 15-20 With). [1,5]. In total, 0.8 ml (1/2 carpule) of anesthetic is enough to anesthetize one single-root tooth under a metal-ceramic

crown (both on the upper and lower jaws). This technique ensures the effectiveness and safety of the injection [1,8,9]. Anesthesia of multi-rooted teeth (molars) in the upper and lower jaws is carried out by other methods - they use conduction anesthesia, etc.

Research results.

For objectification by patients of the assessment of their pain sensations, a 5-point system was used, according to which all degrees of pain during dental interventions were determined [1]:

- 1 - no analgesic effect;
- 2 - weak anesthesia - anesthesia 20-30%;
- 3 - medium anesthesia - anesthesia 30-70%;
- 4 - mild pain during intervention - anesthesia 70-95%;
- 5 - absolute painlessness of the intervention - 100% anesthesia.

Of the 116 injection paraapical anesthesia performed

- pain relief of 5 points was observed in 105 teeth, which

amounted to 90.51% of all teeth subject to anesthesia;

- pain relief of 4 points was observed in 7 teeth, which

respectively amounted to 6.03%;

- anesthesia of 3 points was observed in 4 teeth (3.44%) and was insufficient, and therefore an additional injection of anesthetic was carried out to prepare these teeth. Therefore, in 90.51% of cases, anesthesia made it possible to obtain high-quality anesthesia of individual single-rooted teeth for their preparation for metal-ceramic crowns.

The advantages of the proposed paraapical anesthesia are as follows:

- the use of a standard carpool syringe, an affordable and widely used dental injection instrument;

- an injection of 0.8 ml (1/2 cartridge) of anesthetic is enough to anesthetize one single-root tooth under a ceramic-metal crown, which significantly reduces the toxicity of the injection and allows (if necessary) to anesthetize several teeth, which are often located in different quadrants of the upper and lower jaws, for preparation in one visit; - the slow introduction of an anesthetic solution ensures high-quality saturation of the soft tissues of the paraapical areas of the corresponding tooth with an anesthetic, which provides long-term anesthesia sufficient for the preparation of one single-root tooth for a metal-ceramic crown.

Conclusions

1. The proposed paraapical anesthesia of individual single-rooted teeth showed its effectiveness in 90.51% of cases.

2. The use of a carpool syringe makes anesthesia affordable, and the use of 0.8 ml (1/2 carpool) of anesthetic for anesthesia of one tooth reduces the toxicity of the injection and saves the anesthetic.

References:

1. Kononenko Ju.G. Mestnoe obezboľivanie v ambulatornoj stomatologii.- 5-e izd., pererab. i dop. / Ju.G. Kononenko, N.M. Rozhko, G.P. Ruzin. – M.: Kniga pljus, 2012. – 304 s.

2. Val'chuk O.G. Morfologichna charakteristika reakcii tkanin zuba na etapah likuvannja metalokeramichnimi koronkami v eksperimenti / O.G. Val'chuk, O.O. Kocjura // Materiali dop. nauk.-prakt. konf. Z mizhnar. uchastju "Suchasna rekonstruktivna stomatologija. Mizhdisciplinarnij pidhid". – Odesa, 2012. – S. 31 – 33.

3. Stomatologija / [M.M. Rozhko, I.I. Kirilenko, O.G. Denisenko ta in.]; za red. prof. M.M. Rozhka. — Kn. 2.- K.: VSV «Medicina», 2013. – S. 623 – 656.

4. Stomatologija / [M.M. Rozhko, Z.B. Popovich, V.D. Kuroedova ta in.]; za red. prof. M.M. Rozhka. – Kn. 1.- K.: VSV «Medicina», 2013. – S. 62 – 268.

5. Zastosuvannja karpul'nogo in'ektora FALCON dlja znebolennja nizhnih moljariv / Ju.G. Kononenko, M.M. Rozhko, V.V. Mul'kevich [ta in.] // Materiali dop. mizhnar. nauk.-prakt. konf. "Epidemiologija osnovnih stomatologichnih zahvorjuvan". – Ivano-Frankivs'k, 2004. – S. 53 – 54.

6. Osnovi stomatologii / [V.O. Malanchuk, V.V. Borisenko, L.V. Harkov ta in.]; za red. V.O. Malanchuka. – K.: Medicina, 2009. – S. 286 – 300.

7. Dovidnik stomatologa (metodi obstezhennja, diagnostika, klinika, likuvannja): [navch. posib.] / [Ju.G. Kononenko, M.M. Rozhko, G.V. Kindrat ta in.]. – Ivano-Frankivs'k: NAIR, 2013. – 384 s.

8. Kononenko Ju.G. Efektivne ta bezpechne in'ekcijne znebolennja minimal'nimi dozami anestetika / Ju.G. Kononenko // Stomatolog. – 2004. – №4. – S.18 – 24.

9. Nevidkladni stani na ambulatornomu prijomi u stomatologa: [navch. posib.] / [I.G. Kupnovic'ka, Ju.G. Kononenko, N.V. Nejko, M.M. Rozhko]. – Ivano-Frankivs'k., 2006. – 220 s.